

THE PART OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION

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Annotation The reason of instructing computer science and data innovation to students is to educate them how to utilize advanced computer strategies and technologies, to create abilities in working with advanced computer program. It consists of instructing understudies how to utilize cutting edge computer innovation effectively and how to apply recently created computer program to different divisions of the economy. The science of informatics and data innovation depends on a number of disciplines that shape the premise of different disciplines. It is closely related to the disciplines that serve as the premise for different specialties.

Keywords: Informatics, data advances, showcase economy, cutting edge science, competitive, preparing.

XXI century - the century of building and innovation. Yes, the title was not given in unsuccessful. Natural occasions have fortified intrigued in Its ponder. This interest has been taken after by uncommon revelations within the field of science. Surprising news is being made day by day. The oddity and uniqueness of information and communication innovations is that, in terms of human development, they can enter into nearly all regions of human movement, and can be utilized for a boundless number of places and purposes. Such data and communication advances permit us to overcome obstacles within the handle of human improvement with unprecedented efficiency in three regions:

1) Overcoming impediments within the way of procuring information. The utilize of information is vital for forming human potential for learning. On the off chance that instruction leads to the advancement of cognitive aptitudes, data will be

required to provide an important perspective of the information securing handle. The Web and the World Wide Web are the same data recovery channels for individuals from all strolls of life.

2) Removes boundaries to social life. The capacity to communicate with the world through the Web has empowered the spread of numerous worldwide civic activities in recent a long time. For illustration, criticism within the instruction framework. 3) Expels boundaries to financial development. ICT and related businesses and the education framework are the quickest developing divisions. Unused data innovations dramatically grow get to data and communication. Email, e-libraries - locales give boundless openings for the instruction framework, break down any boundaries, give get to instructive and scientific information from anywhere within the world. Information and instructive exercises. The globalization of instruction - from seminars to psychological warfare and devout radicalism - has expanded the significance of information and instructive openings. New data advances permit science and instruction to be connected to closer and more viable channels, such as the conveyance, recharging, and reassessment of collected information.

Today, science is the most, prevailing device for the improvement of the instruction system. This has changed the importance of science within the instruction framework, which has not continuously been the case with progressed data innovation. Society makes an unused logical structure, which is related not as it were with the development of science itself, but too with the framework of instruction and preparing. There are presently around 2.5 billion one of a kind freely utilized web pages on the Web, with 7.3 million unused ones included each day. At the same time, these developments, in specific, different contraptions, gadgets and devices are getting to be an indispensably part of human life. Viable utilize of them could be a topical issue nowadays. In this regard, the intensive ponder of the subject "Advanced computer equipment and software" in Uzbekistan, beside the information of theoretical materials, serves as an aptitude within the academic movement of

understudies. Students will learn about the interrelationships and methodological interrelationships of science with other disciplines in the curriculum and the methods of teaching in practice.

Learning in casual settings, such as historical centers and after-school clubs, can interface educational substance with issues that matter to learners in their lives. These connections work in both headings. Learning in schools and colleges can be enhanced by encounters from ordinary life; casual learning can be developed by including questions and information from the classroom. These associated encounters start assist intrigued and motivation to memorize. A successful strategy is for an educator to propose and discuss an address within the classroom, at that

point for learners to investigate that address on a historical center visit or field trip, collecting photographs or notes as prove, at that point share their discoveries back in the class to deliver person or bunch answers. These hybrid learning encounters misuse the qualities of both situations and give learners with true and locks in openings for learning. Since learning occurs over a lifetime, drawing on experiences across multiple settings, the wider opportunity is to support learners in recording, linking, recalling and sharing their diverse learning events.

The study of methodological science prepares students to independently and consciously address issues of teaching and educating students, as well as to continue the independent study of the theory and practice of education, to read recently distributed methodological writing, prepares you with the abilities required to structurally assess and generalize your composing encounter. Incidental learning is impromptu or inadvertent learning. It may happen whereas carrying out a movement that's apparently disconnected to what is learned. Early research on this theme managed with how individuals learn in their day by day schedules at their workplaces. For numerous individuals, versatile gadgets have been coordinates into their everyday lives, providing numerous openings for technology-supported accidental learning. Unlike formal education, incidental learning isn't driven by an instructor, nor does it follow an organized educational programs, or result in formal certification. However, it may trigger self-reflection and this can be utilized to energize learners to reconceive what seem something else be isolated learning fragments as part of more coherent and longer-term learning ventures. Computational considering may be an effective approach to considering and issue fathoming.

It includes breaking huge issues down into littler ones (decay), recognizing how these relate to issues that have been illuminated within the past (pattern acknowledgment), setting aside insignificant subtle elements (reflection), identifying and creating the steps that will be fundamental to reach an arrangement (algorithms) and refining these steps (investigating). Such computational

considering abilities can be profitable in numerous angles of life, ranging from composing a formula to share a favorite dish with companions, through planning an occasion or undertaking, to sending a logical group to handle a difficult challenge like an episode of infection. The point is to educate children to structure issues so they can be illuminated. Computational considering can be instructed as portion of science, science and craftsmanship or in other settings. The point isn't fair to empower children to be computer coders, but moreover to ace a craftsmanship of considering that will empower them to handle complex challenges in all angles of their lives.

Epitomized learning includes self-awareness of the body collaboration with a genuine or simulated world to bolster the learning handle. When learning a modern wear, physical development is a self-evident portion of the learning handle. In epitomized learning, the point is that intellect and body work together so that physical criticism and activities strengthen the learning prepare. Technology to help this incorporates wearable sensors that accumulate individual physical and organic information, visual frameworks that track development, and portable gadgets that respond to activities such as tilting and movement.

This approach can be connected to the investigation of angles of physical sciences such as contact, increasing speed, and drive, or to explore mimicked circumstances such as the structure of atoms. For more common learning, the method of physical activity gives a way to engage learners in feeling as they learn. Being more mindful of how one's body interacts with the world can moreover bolster the advancement of a careful approach to learning and well-being.

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